

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Scientometric Analysis and Collaboration Trends of Published Literature by State Universities from West Bengal

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Abstract

The study examines the analysis of research output by the Universities of West Bengal from 2002 to 2021. Journal articles are the most preferred form of publication type of documents by the Universities of West Bengal. It shows the highest RGR value among seven universities is obtained by Vidyasagar University in the year 2021 and the lowest value is obtained by the University of Calcutta in the year 2021. The study used Domestic Collaboration and International Collaboration and it shows the highest paper 11529 (38.38%) was published at the domestic level and international level 3140 (43.87%) by Jadavpur University. It found that 16.82 % of the total publications are open access research articles with 6255. It is quite interesting to know that Jadavpur University has a significant lead towards encouraging the researcher to publish in open access journals with 33.78%. The most productive author is Subhadeep Das, Department of Life Sci. & Biotechnology, Jadavpur University with 908 articles ranked in first place among the universities studied.

Keywords: Scientometrics; Exponential growth rate; Domestic collaboration; International collaboration; Relative citation impact; Impact factor

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1. Introduction

Higher education means different things to various people. In terms of level, higher education entails obtaining a higher educational qualification through the teaching-learning process in higher educational institutions such as colleges and universities. Higher education is considered as an opportunity to engage in the individual's development process through a flexible education method, as well as an input to the growth and development of the industry.

The higher education system is important to the country's entire growth, including industrial, social, and economic development. India's higher education system is the world's third-largest. At present time, the role of Indian higher educational institutes such as colleges and universities is to give quality-based education in the fields of education, research, and other areas to equip youth for self-sufficiency.

The vision of the Government of India in the field of higher education is to make institutions of higher learning emerge as centers of innovation, excellence, and development. The main focus is on quality. The mission is to provide world-class quality

education, opening higher education portals for students from rural and backward areas and marginalized families.

The indexes of Scopus, owned by Elsevier, and the indexed Web of Science owned by Clarivate Analytics are two scientometric collections that can be accessed both directly and through secondary data sources. Scopus and WoS have theoretical, practical, and empirical-analytical functions. They define the boundaries of acknowledged global knowledge, supply content for networked epistemic collaboration and interchange, and serve as a source for university research output. Scientometric enables the categorization and analyze papers, authors, scientific groups, and citations based on discipline, topic, institutional affiliation, demographics, and geographic location. This enormous data set is used for a variety of scientific and performance applications.

2. Literature review

(Shariatmadari & Mahdi, 2012) analyzed the research output of research productivity in Islamic Azad University. This paper is aimed to explore the existing barriers to research productivity based on faculty members'